

Evaluation of Thyroid Gland Hormones among Women with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome

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Abstract:

Objective: The study aims to determine the effects of PCOS on some thyroid hormones and to find the relationship between PCOS and the hormones T3, T4, and TSH in the population of Karbala. It is a case-control study that includes PCOS patients and a healthy control group. **Method:** The research was carried out during a period beginning in January 2024 and ending in March 2024. At the Obstetrics and Gynecology Teaching Hospital, Karbala Health Directorate. A case-control study was performed on 50 PCOS patients out of 50 healthy controls. After obtaining participants' information, a blood sample was drawn from venipuncture. T3/T4/TSH parameters were checked. **Result:** 50 women of PCOS

and 50 healthy women, the results of patients are T3 (1.97), T4(85.92), TSH (1.82). **Conclusion:** Through our study, we conclude that there is an increase in the levels of T3/T4 hormones and a decrease in the level of TSH in the group, which is related to the effect of polycystic ovary syndrome on the patient. Thus, we conclude that there is a relationship between polycystic ovary disease and thyroid disease.

Keywords: PCOS, T3, T4, TSH, thyroid disease.

Introduction

An endocrine condition that frequently affects women during their reproductive years is polycystic ovarian syndrome. It is regarded as a complicated metabolic illness that can have long-term effects on metabolism and reproduction (Bjekić-Macut et al., 2021). Insulin resistance and elevated testosterone levels are linked to the main pathophysiological pathways. Currently, it is recognized that PCOS has genetic roots, with many genes contributing to the etiology of insulin resistance, inflammation, hyperandrogenism, and abnormal folliculogenesis (Mousa et al., 2019).

Studies have linked PCOS to a myriad of co-morbidities, including endometrial cancer,

obesity, type 2 diabetes (T2D), depression, anxiety, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease, sleep apnea, and eating disorders (Horne et al., 2022). For decades, researchers and medical professionals have attempted to comprehend the intricate interplay between hereditary and environmental factors that contribute to the pathophysiology of polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), but they have not been able to come to a consensus (Lizneva et al., 2016).

the prevalence of chronic illness, the limitations of current technology, and the knowledge required to identify certain pathogenic pathways in intricate and developing scientific fields (Jason et al., 2011). Most people agree that a variety of lifestyle factors, such as nutrition, exercise, obesity, and environmental pollutants, as well as

genetic, epigenetic, molecular biology, and in utero developmental programming, contribute to the pathophysiology of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) (Goodarzi et al., 2011; Mohsein et al., 2024). It is also acknowledged that a variety of lifestyle-based therapies can be used to treat, regulate, and even reverse many of the biochemical, metabolic, endocrine, and phenotypic aspects of PCOS (Frayling et al., 2018). It may be the cause of infertility in many cases. PCOS results in the production of cysts in the antral follicles of female ovarian tissue and is caused by an imbalance of sex hormones. The egg is surrounded by fluid-filled sacs that create a cyst. A functional cyst is described as an egg that transforms into a cyst and further delays ovulation (Voight et al., 2012).

PCOS-affected women show increased risks of gestation complications including miscarriage, gestational diabetes, hypertension, and preeclampsia. Due to these difficulties, most women face premature delivery resulting in caesarean section (Abbott DH et al., 2019).

The prevalence of PCOS changes with the diagnostic criteria. By combining all the three criteria, incidence rates were reported as low as 1.6% and as high as 18% in similar Caucasian populations using the Rotterdam criteria. It has also been reported that 50%–75% women with polycystic ovaries were unaware and remain undiagnosed. Considering symptom (Reyes-Muñoz et al., 2012). Numerous cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk factors, including obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and hypertension, are

linked to polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) (Rodgers et al., 2019).

Materials and Methods

The research was carried out during a period beginning in January 2024 and ending in February 2024. At the Obstetrics and Gynecology Teaching Hospital, Karbala Health Directorate. A case-control study was performed on 50 PCOS patients and 50 healthy controls. All of the women patients were adults, between the ages of twenty and forty-five. After obtaining participants' information, a blood sample was drawn from venipuncture. T3/T4/TSH parameters were checked. There was a lot of vital information and data collected from the patients, such as their names, age, blood group, chronic disease. automated analysis to (TSH, T3, T4) by MAGLUMI device.

Results and Discussion

General Features of PCOS Patients

Table (1) indicates that the highest percentage was O+, which is 52.0% for control, while the highest percentage was 72.0% for patient, and the percentage was A+44.0%, A- 0.0%, and B+4.0% for control, while for patient, the percentage was A+, which was 16.0% and A- 4.0. % and B + 8.0%, and the percentage of control numbers for age groups less than 30 is 44.0% and more than 30 is 56.0%. As for the percentage of patients for age groups less than 30 is 64.0% and above 30 is 36.0%.

Table 1. Distribution and Characteristics of Patients and Control According to the Blood Group

Variable	Level	Control		Patient		Total		P-Value
		Number	Percentage %	Number	Percentage %	Number	Percentage %	
Blood Group	A+	11	44.0%	4	16.0%	15	30.0%	0.114
	A-	0	0.0%	1	4.0%	1	2.0%	
	B+	1	4.0%	2	8.0%	3	6.0%	
	O+	13	52.0%	18	72.0%	31	62.0%	
Age Group	Less than 30	11	44.0%	16	64.0%	27	54.0%	0.156
	Greater than 30	14	56.0%	9	36.0%	23	46.0%	

Note: The chi-square test has been utilized to analyze the categorical variables. *. Association is significant at the 0.05 level.

Figure (1) (2) indicates that the highest percentage was O+, which is 52.0% for control, while the highest percentage was 72.0% for patient, and the percentage was A+44.0%, A-0.0%, and B+4.0% for control, while for patient, the percentage was A+, which was 16.0% and A-

4.0. % and B + 8.0%, and the percentage of control numbers for age groups less than 30 is 44.0% and more than 30 is 56.0%. As for the percentage of patients for age groups less than 30 is 64.0% and above 30 is 36.0%.

Figure 1. Distribution and Characteristics of Patients and Control According to Blood Group

Figure 2. Distribution and Characteristics of Patients and Control According to Age Group

our outcome as shown in Table 1 that appear not correlation between ABO/Rh blood groups and PCOS. Agreement with a recent study that indicates, the characteristics of clinical and biochemical parameters were contrasted based on ABO/Rh blood groups. There were 265 patients that took part in the trial. The most common symptoms at the time of diagnosis were oligomenorrhea (80.9%) and hirsutism (86%) . Sixty-six (62.6%) of the patients had

baseline ultrasonography results that were compatible with PCOS. Insulin resistance was discovered in 111 (41.9%) of the individuals. The patient's and control groups' ABO blood group distributions were found to be similar ($P = 9$). Oligomenorrhea, hirsutism, hair loss, acne, obesity, high testosterone levels, insulin resistance, and ultrasonography characteristics did not differ across ABO/Rh blood groups. The distribution of ABO/Rh blood groups in

PCOS patients was found to be comparable to that of healthy individuals in this study, indicating that ABO/Rh blood groups were not associated with an increased risk of PCOS (Schussler et al., 1990). Disagreement with previous study demonstrated that. According to their research, the blood group distribution in all control cohorts showed that blood group O was significantly less common and blood group A was much more common in patients with ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome. The early-onset type of this syndrome was found in patients with blood group O versus A undergoing controlled ovarian stimulation at an odds ratio of 2.171 (p-value 0.002) (Binder et al., 2008).

In another study showed that the fact that most of the patients were under 35 years old may account for the slight hormonal variations. Notwithstanding these drawbacks, this is the first study to shed light on how PCOS characteristics vary over time in a sizable cohort of women (Sun et al., 2022).

Our result in table 1 not disagreement with this consideration that The degree of PCOS diagnosis may vary depending on the participants' age. Individuals diagnosed with PCOS based on the 2003 Rotterdam criteria may exhibit distinct phenotypes based on their age group. In a cross-sectional study involving 453 PCOS-affected women, we showed that younger women had a considerably higher percentage of

than older women among those who met the diagnostic criteria for PCOS (Jacewicz-Święcka et al., 2021).

And some literatures disagreement with our results about Clinical data from 1690 Chinese Han women treated with IVF/ICSI-ET were gathered for the retrospective cohort study from hospital records between April 2019 and March 2020 at the Southwest Medical University associated hospital in Liuzhou, China. LH and E2 differences were not statistically significant, but differences in age, length of infertility, BMI, FSH, FSH / LH (Brown et al., 2011).

Our results disagreements with these study that with age, there are changes in the predominance of PCOS phenotypes. More precisely, there was no discernible difference in the distribution of phenotypes between patients under 20 and patients between 21 and 30 years old. On the other hand, phenotype 1, which is typified by anovulation and polycystic ovarian syndrome, has been found to be less common (Hsu et al., 2013).

Biochemical Parameters

Thyroid gland hormones and age in PCOS patients

Results in table (2) showed no significant differences (p < 0.05) between age and thyroid diseases (T3, T4, TSH).

Table 2. The Comparisons between Research Parameters in Patients According to the Age Group

Parameters	Age Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	P-Value
T3	Less than 30	2.26	1.68	0.076
	Greater than 30	1.45	0.16	
T4	Less than 30	84.85	10.93	0.486
	Greater than 30	87.84	8.45	
TSH	Less than 30	1.69	0.75	0.347
	Greater than 30	2.05	1.12	

Note: It has proven possible to identify statistically significant differences between several independent groups by using Kruskal-Wallis tests; *. At the 0.05 level, the mean difference is significant.

Our results in table 2 disagreements with these study that found patients under the age of 25

made up the largest group of thyroid patients, with nearly half of them having PCOS and

falling between the 26–35 age category (48%) (Pervin et al., 2020).

Another study our result in table 2 not suitable with these saw that is present in 4–10% of the general population (Kamrul-Hasan et al., 2020). however, the frequency is 2% in young women between the ages of 12 and 39.2,3 Common symptoms of PCOS and overt hypothyroidism include irregular menstruation, oligo/anovulation, subfertility, miscarriage, and

polycystic appearance of the ovaries (AL-Jumaili et al., 2020).

Comparison thyroid gland hormones between patients and control

Result in table (4-4) revealed high high significant differences ($p = 0.0001$) between TSH and PCOS, while in the same table showed high significant differences ($p = 0.013$) between T3 and PCOS , finally that table appeared high

Table 3. The Comparisons between Research Parameters in Patients and Their Controls

Parameters	Case	Mean	Std. Deviation	P-Value
T3	Control	1.33	0.16	0.013*
	Patient	1.97	1.39	
T4	Control	81.86	9.79	0.045*
	Patient	85.92	10.03	
TSH	Control	2.21	1.63	0.0001**
	Patient	1.82	0.89	

Note: It has proven possible to identify statistically significant differences between several independent groups by using Kruskal-Wallis tests; *. At the 0.05 level, the mean difference is significant.

Figure 3. The Comparisons between T3 Level in Patients and Their Controls

Figure 4. The Comparisons between T4 Level in Patients and Their Controls

Figure (3) (4) indicates that the highest percentage was O+, which is 52.0% for control, while the highest percentage was 72.0% for patient, and the percentage was A+44.0%, A-0.0%, and B+4.0% for control, while for patient, the percentage was A+, which was 16.0% and A-4.0. % and B + 8.0%, and the percentage of control numbers for age groups less than 30 is 44.0% and more than 30 is 56.0%. As for the

percentage of patients for age groups less than 30 is 64.0% and above 30 is 36.0%.

TSH levels were higher in a greater proportion of PCOS patients than in the control group . Furthermore, a statistically significant correlation was found between several PCOS characteristics and blood TSH levels (Lee et al., 2023).

Figure 5. The Comparisons between TSH Level in Patients and Their Controls

Disagreements with the findings of a recent with this consideration that High risks of pregnancy problems and elevated levels of circulating thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) are associated with women with polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) (Garcia-Beltran et al., 2023).

It also contradicts previous studies that as evidenced by the results of this study, PCOS patients had a higher prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism than healthy subjects. Metabolic indicators, except for HDL, were not different between PCOS patients with and without hypothyroidism (Bonakdaran et al., 2023).

Our result in table 4 disagreement with these consideration that The current findings showed that the patient's group had significantly higher levels of TSH, LH, and FSH ($P < 0.05$), while the PCOS females group had lower blood triiodothyronine levels. The current study's findings indicated that PCOS patients had hypothyroidism, as seen by higher levels of TSH, LH, and FSH (Deli et al., 2024). In another study indicated assessed the levels of TSH, T3, T4, and testosterone in women in Babylon City who had polycystic ovarian syndrome. Based on statistical analysis, it was determined that there were differences between the patient and control groups ($P < 0.05$) and that the levels of T3, T4, TSH, and testosterone were elevated in polycystic ovary compared to the healthy control group (Mirdanalsaad et al., 2020).

Conclusion

This study aims to determine the impact of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) on thyroid disease and to explore the relationship between the hormones T3, T4, and TSH. It involved 50 healthy individuals and 50 patients. The findings revealed that age and blood type do not influence the illness, but a significant relationship exists between PCOS and thyroid gland dysfunction. Specifically, the results indicated an increase in T3 and T4 levels, accompanied by a decrease in TSH levels.

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